

THE EFFECT OF A SLIGHT INTERFACIAL REACTION ON THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF SQUEEZE-CAST SiCp/6061 AL COMPOSITES

Yan Cui, Lin Geng, Congkai Yao, Xiaoli Li

*P.O. Box 433, School of Materials Science and Engineering
Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin 150001, P.R. China*

SUMMARY: A slight interfacial reaction was observed in squeeze-cast SiCp/6061Al composites, and this kind of reaction was found to have a particular effect on the mechanical properties of the composites. The results of flexure tests show that this reaction in the composite obviously increases the elastic properties, but it is not beneficial to the fracture strength and ductility. This phenomenon can be interpreted in terms of two different micromechanisms which were analyzed using TEM and HREM observations, acoustic emission (AE) technique and SEM fractography. In addition, a new method of SiC surface modification which can control the interface state was initially presented.

KEYWORDS: SiCp/Al composites, slight interfacial reaction, mechanical behaviour, keying in, crack initiation

INTRODUCTION

The interface between reinforcement and matrix is currently attracting the maximum attention as a result of its nature plays a critical role in influencing the properties and strengthening mechanism of metal matrix composites (MMCs). For SiCp/Al composites, it is believed that a strong interface is necessary for the production of high-dislocation density and effective transfer of load from matrix to the reinforcement, resulting in an increased elastic modulus and strength[1-4]. Since SiC-Al system is out of equilibrium, chemical reactions may occur at interfacial area during the fabrication or service involved high temperatures[5]. Moreover, the interface bond strength is controlled to a large extent by the reactions. Therefore, by understanding the detailed chemical reaction and its effect, it may be possible to control the reaction, which in turn tailor the interfacial properties and overall mechanical behaviour of SiCp/Al composites to meet the specific requirements for various applications[6]. Considerable previous investigations have shown that the formation of a significant amount of brittle compound such as Al_4C_3 or $MgAl_2O_4$ at the Al/SiC interface is detrimental to the stiffness and strength of the composites[7,8]. Compared with the excessive reactions as mentioned above, very few studies have been carried out on a slight interfacial reaction in SiCp/Al composites[4,9], in particular, the effect of this type of reaction has never been reported, which may hinder the design, development and application of the composites.

The aim of this paper is therefore to study the effect of a slight interfacial reaction on the mechanical properties of SiCp/6061Al composites, with particular emphasis on the extent of the reaction and the mechanisms of its effect on mechanical properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

Commercial 6061 aluminium alloy was used as the matrix and angular-shaped SiC particulate with a mean size of about 3.5 μ m was used as the reinforcement. For comparison purposes, some of SiC particulates had been treated in hydrofluoric acid before the fabrication of the composites. Both composites (with the volume fraction of 45% as-received or treated SiC particulates) are fabricated by the squeeze casting method with the same process parameters, namely, the preform without using any binder was preheated with mold in air to 580°C before squeeze casting. Molten Al alloy at 800°C was then poured into the mold, followed by hydraulic compressing under high pressure of 100MPa.

Interface characterization was carried out using TEM and HREM, microscopy samples were observed in detail by Philips CM-12 transmission electron microscope equipped with EDAX system operating at 120kV and JEOL2000EX-II high resolution electron transmission microscope operating at 200kV. Flexure tests were performed on an Instron 1186 universal testing machine at a crosshead speed of 0.5mm/min to determine the mechanical properties of composites. A minimum of 7 specimens was tested for each type of material to eliminate possible segregation effects and to obtain a mean value and standard deviation which would be representative of the materials. All specimens were 3.0 \times 4.0 \times 36.0 mm according to JIS specification. In order to further understand the interfacial effect and its micromechanism, acoustic emissions were monitored during the flexure testing until failure, and then, fractographs were examined using S-570 scanning electron microscope .

RESULTS

Interface Microstructure

Fig.1(a) is a typical TEM micrograph of the interface in as-cast 6061 Al matrix composites reinforced with the as-received SiC particulates, showing the presence of the isolated reaction product particles with a size of about 50-100nm at SiC-Al interface. These fine particles grow from the SiC surface into the Al matrix, and most of them have angular shapes. These reaction products were clearly identified as spinel MgAl₂O₄ by the EDAX and SADP as shown in Fig.1(b), (c) and (d). In order to further determine the extent of the interfacial reaction, chemical analysis of matrix was carried out using inductively coupled plasma-atomic emission spectrometer. The results showed that the content of Mg in the matrix decreased to 0.69% (from 1.03% in 6061 Al) as a result of the chemical reaction. Based on the amount of the depletion of Mg in the matrix arising from the interfacial reaction and the area of interface/per unit volume (this magnitude was determined by means of the density, volume fraction and specific surface area of SiC particulate), it can be calculated that about 10~20 % of SiC particulate surface was covered by this kind of reaction product, which in turn confirm that the extent of interfacial reaction which had taken place during the fabrication of the composites reinforced with as-received SiC particulates is slight. The formation mechanism of the reaction products is discussed as follows:

Practically, the as-received SiC particulates had always been slightly oxidized before the fabrication of the composites, which had been confirmed using XPS. Thus, the thin native SiO₂ layer around the as-received SiC particulates will firstly react with molten 6061 Al alloy (containing 1.03% Mg element) to form MgAl₂O₄ accords to Eq. (1) during the squeeze casting. Due to the very short time of the contact between SiC and liquid Al alloy (about a few seconds), no further reactions (such as Al₄C₃ formation) occur. In such case, MgAl₂O₄ spinel is the only one type of interfacial compound.

For comparison purpose, the interface of composites with as-treated (acid washed) SiC particulates was examined using TEM and HREM. It can be seen from Fig.2 that the interface is clean as expected, and there is no reaction product or amorphous transition layer. In such cases, the native SiO₂ layer had been removed prior to the composites fabrication as a result of hydrofluoric acid can dissolved the oxide layer easily. In general, the SiC particulates without oxide cover were rejected from the molten Al alloy, but, the composites can be fabricated by squeeze casting technique successfully (without forming the voids at the interfaces, and the SiC is perfectly bonded to the matrix), which is attributed to the high pressure role.

*Fig.1: (a) TEM micrograph showing the interfacial reaction products
 (b) EDAX spectrum for the interfacial reaction product in (a)
 (c), (d) Two zone axes SADP obtained from the interfacial reaction products in (a)*

Fig.2: (a) TEM micrograph of the interface in the composite with treated SiC particulates
(b) HREM image of area A in (a)

Flexural Properties

The effect of the thin SiO_2 layer on processing is considered to be beneficial as it appears to improve the wettability of the SiC by liquid aluminum and facilitate the fabrication of SiCp/Al composites, but the effect of the thin layer and the slight interfacial reaction arising from it on mechanical behaviour of the composites still be unknown, which may hinder the development and application of this kind of material. Since perfect SiCp/Al composites with the clean interface have been obtained at the same processing condition except the chemical nature of SiC, it is possible to investigate the law of the above effect. The effect was evaluated using the flexure tests. The results are shown in Table 1. It is evident from Table 1 that the interfacial reaction can have a significant effect on the flexural properties of the composites. As compared to the composites with clean interface, the presence of the fine particulates of MgAl_2O_4 at interface results in 11.4% and 7.3% increase in elastic modulus and elastic limit (0.01 offset) respectively, at the same time, 11.8% decrease in ultimate flexural strength was observed. In addition, the interfacial reaction caused 30.5% decrease in the fracture strain of the composites also.

Table 1: Effect of the slight interfacial reaction on the mechanical properties* of SiCp/6061Al composites

SPECIMEN	E (GPa)	$\sigma_{0.01}$ (MPa)	σ_{fs} (MPa)	ϵ_f (%)
reacted interface	164.9(± 2.1)	156.7(± 6.6)	497.8(± 7.2)	0.73(± 0.03)
clean interface	148.0(± 2.9)	146.0(± 4.5)	564.4(± 13.7)	1.05(± 0.03)

* Shown in parentheses are the standard deviation of samples

DISCUSSION

The micromechanisms of the above particular effect law are now discussed respectively as follows:

Firstly, the discrete particles of compound that are "keyed in" to both phases (as shown in Fig 1) may enhance the bonding of the interface (by the strong chemical bonding and mechanical keying), additionally, they may inhibit the plastic deformation of near-interface matrix when subjected to lower stress level also, thus, improving the load transfer, consequently, enhanced elastic properties were observed.

*Fig.3 SEM fractographs of flexure tested specimens
(a) fracture surface of the composite with the interfacial reaction products
(b) fracture surface of the composite with clean interface*

Secondly, the above "keying in" mechanism might not be responsible for the observed decrease in both fracture strength and ductility. Therefore, the mechanism which can explain the above mentioned degraded properties was investigated using acoustic emission (AE) technique and SEM fractography. The AE signal and stress-strain curve corresponding to it indicated that the decohesion of the interface with reaction products occurs earlier than that of the clean interface, the details of AE response have been described elsewhere [10]. This is due to the brittleness of $MgAl_2O_4$ (its fracture toughness is only one-third of that of SiC). The reaction product is a weak region which is prone to initiate microcrack when subjected to the higher stress level. In addition, the SEM fractographs (as shown in Fig.3) of two kinds of composites after the flexure tests show that the interface debonding without significant deformation of the matrix near the SiC particulate is the major fracture mode of the composites with the reaction products; on the contrary, a large deformation of matrix had occurred around the SiC particulate before interfacial debonding in the composites with clean interface, which suggests that this interface is strong enough to permit the effective transfer of load from matrix to the reinforcement. The SEM observation further confirms the results of AE analysis, namely, the initiation of microcrack in reaction products is accounted for the premature interfacial debonding and some properties degrading.

CONCLUSIONS

1. At lower stress level, the slight interfacial reaction results in the enhanced elastic properties through "keying in" mechanism. Whereas for higher stress level, the reaction degrades the fracture strength and ductility through "crack initiation" mechanism.
2. The suitable acid treatment can modify the interface state and its bond strength, which in turn realize the control and optimization of the overall mechanical properties of SiCp/6061Al composites to maximize its performance in specific application .

REFERENCES

1. Feest, E.A., "Interfacial Phenomena in Metal Matrix Composites", *Composites*. Vol. 25, 1994, pp75-81
2. Ribes, H., Suery, M., Eseperance, G.L. and Legoux, J.G., "Microscopic Emiamination of the Interface Region in 6061- Al SiC Composites Reinforced with As-Received and Oxidized SiC Particles", *Metall.Trans.*, Vol. 21A, 1990, pp 2489
3. Li,S., Arsenault, R.J. and Jena, P., "Quantum Chemical Study of Adhesion at the SiC/Al Interface", *J.Appl.Phys.*, Vol. 64, 1988, pp 6246
4. Wang Ning, Wang Zhirui and George C. Weatherly, "Formation of Magnesium Aluminate (Spinel) in Cast SiC Particulate-Reinforced Al (A356) Metal Matrix Composites", *Metall.Trans.*, Vol. 23A, 1992, pp1423-1430
5. Boq-Kong Hwo, Su-Jien Lin, Min-Ten Jahn, "The Interfacial Compounds and SEM Fractography of Squeeze-Cast SiCp/6061 Al Composites", *Mater.Sci.Eng.*, Vol. A206, 1996, pp110-119
6. Foo, K.S., Banks,W.M., Craven, A.J. and Hendry,A., "Interface Characterization of an SiC Particulate/6061 Aluminium Alloy Composite", *Composites.*, Vol. 25, 1994, pp677-683
7. Ribes, H., Silva, R.Da., Suery, M. and Brtheau,T., "Effect of Interfacial Oxide Layer in Al-SiC Particle Composites on Bond Strength and Mechanical Behaviour", *Mater.Sci.Tech.*, Vol.6, 1990, pp 621-628
8. Vedani,M., Gariboldi, E., Silva, G. and Gregorio,C.Di., "Influence of Interface Properties on Mechanical Behaviour of Particle Reinforced Metal Matrix Composite", *Mater.Sci.Tech.*, Vol.10, 1994, pp132-140
9. Salvo,L., LEsperance,G., Suery, M.and Legoux ,J.G., "Interfacial Reactions and Age Hardening in Al-Mg-Si Metal Matrix Composites Reinforced with SiC Particles", *Mater.Sci.Eng.*, Vol.A177, 1994, pp173-183
10. Cui, Y., Geng, L. and Yao, C.K., "Interfacial Control and Wavelet Analysis of Acoustic Emission Behaviours in SiCp/Al Composites", *Acta Metallurgica Sinica* (in Chinese), to be published